

Synthesis, characterization and biological studies of dioxouranium(II) and thorium(IV) complexes of Schiff bases derived from 2-aminopyridine and acetophenones

K. B. Gudasi*, G. S. Nadagouda and T. R. Goudar

P. G. Department of Studies in Chemistry, Karnatak University, Dharwad-580 003, Karnataka, India

E-mail : kbgudasi@rediffmail.com Fax : 91-836-721275

Manuscript received 18 July 2005, revised 10 January 2006, accepted 16 January 2006

Abstract : The metal complexes of UO_2^{II} and Th^{IV} with Schiff bases derived from 2-aminopyridine and acetophenone/*o*-hydroxy acetophenone/*o*-amino acetophenone have been synthesized and characterized on the basis of elemental analyses, conductivity, IR, electronic and ^1H NMR spectral studies. The evidences show that the complexes with acetophenone and *o*-hydroxy acetophenone Schiff bases exhibit coordination number eight while coordination number ten with *o*-amino acetophenone Schiff bases. A comparative study of testicular atrophy in albino rats by the chelating agents and the corresponding UO_2^{II} and Th^{IV} complexes was carried out. A considerable reduction in the testes weight and weight of some accessory sex organs was observed. The effect is more with the complexes than with the ligands.

Keywords : Dioxouranium(II), thorium(IV), Schiff base, biological studies.

In continuation of our study on uranium and thorium complexes^{1,2}, here we report the syntheses and characterization of UO_2^{II} and Th^{IV} complexes with Schiff bases derived from 2-aminopyridine and acetophenone, *o*-hydroxy acetophenone and *o*-amino acetophenone. A comparative study of testicular atrophy in albino rats for the ligands as well as the corresponding UO_2^{II} and Th^{IV} complexes was also carried out to know the biological effect of these metal complexes in comparison with the chelating agent.

Results and discussion

The complexes are bright yellow to orange red in colour. These are soluble in DMF and DMSO. The elemental analyses (Table 1) shows that the complexes are with 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry. The molar conductance measurements in DMF at 10^{-3} M concentration fall in the range of $10\text{--}15 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ (Table 1), indicating their non-electrolytic behavior.

Infrared spectra :

Table 2 lists selected vibrational bands and assignments of ligands and their metal complexes. The IR spectra of Schiff bases have shown a fairly sharp band around $1630\text{--}1610 \text{cm}^{-1}$ assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$. In the spectra of the complexes it has shifted to the lower frequency ($\sim 1605\text{--}1590 \text{cm}^{-1}$) region, indicating the coordination of azomethine

group to metal ions³. Two bands at 3430 and 3390cm^{-1} in L_3 are due to symmetric and asymmetric stretching frequencies of NH_2 and have shifted to lower frequency ($\sim 3300\text{--}3250 \text{cm}^{-1}$) suggesting a decrease in the bond order of NH bond on coordination^{4,5}. The complexes show five absorption bands near $1505, 1318, 812, 769 \text{cm}^{-1}$, which are assigned respectively to $\nu_4, \nu_1, \nu_2, \nu_6$ and ν_3 vibrations of the coordinated (C_{2n}) nitrate group. The magnitude of separation of ν_4 and ν_1 is in the range of $195\text{--}200 \text{cm}^{-1}$ indicating that the nitrate groups are coordinated in bidentate fashion^{6,7}. The bands due to pyridine ring vibrations $1565, 1460 \text{cm}^{-1}$ have remained unchanged on complexation indicating the non-involvement of pyridine ring nitrogen in coordination⁸. A typical doublet observed between $920\text{--}890 \text{cm}^{-1}$ was attributed to $\nu_{3\text{asym}}$ and the bands around 820cm^{-1} to $\nu_{1\text{sym}} \text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O}$ stretching vibrations in UO_2^{II} complexes suggesting the linear nature of UO_2 . A broad weak band in the region $2800\text{--}2700 \text{cm}^{-1}$ in the spectrum of L_2 was assigned to intramolecularly hydrogen bonded phenolic vibration. Disappearance of this band in the spectra of C_2 and C_5 complexes indicate the deprotonation and coordination of phenolic oxygen atom. This was further supported by a negative shift of the $\nu(\text{CO})$ phenolic, from around 1260cm^{-1} in the ligand spectrum to around 1250cm^{-1} in the complexes⁹. The intense broad band at $530\text{--}510 \text{cm}^{-1}$ in dioxouranium

complexes was assigned to $\nu(\text{U}-\text{N})$ and the band at 580–570 cm^{-1} to $\nu(\text{Th}-\text{N})$ vibration in Th^{IV} complexes¹⁰.

Table 1. Analytical and conductivity data of the complexes

Code	Complex	M.p. (°C)	Metal (%)	N (%)	Λ_{M} $\Omega \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
C ₁	$[\text{UO}_2(\text{L}_1)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	138	30.01 (30.28)	10.49 (10.69)	15
C ₂	$[\text{UO}_2(\text{L}_2)_2]$	131	34.09 (34.39)	7.96 (8.09)	11
C ₃	$[\text{UO}_2(\text{L}_3)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	132	29.48 (29.17)	13.45 (13.72)	12
C ₄	$[\text{Th}(\text{L}_1)_2(\text{NO}_3)_4]$	110	26.39 (26.61)	12.64 (12.84)	14
C ₅	$[\text{Th}(\text{L}_2)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	115	29.31 (29.82)	10.52 (10.80)	10
C ₆	$[\text{Th}(\text{L}_3)_2(\text{NO}_3)_4]$	111	25.59 (25.72)	15.45 (15.52)	13

The values in the parenthesis are calculated values.

¹H NMR spectra :

The sharp multiple signals of the phenyl protons were noticed in the region 6.27–7.57 ppm. The signals due to NH_2 protons (L_3) has shifted from 2.45 to 2.52 ppm on coordination. The resonance due to *o*-OH group (L_2) at 13.52 ppm disappears on complexation indicating substitution through the -OH of the Schiff base. A downfield shift of $\text{N}=\text{CH}$ resonance was observed on complexation. This was ascribed to the coordination of azomethine nitrogen.

Scheme 1. Synthetic route of the ligands.

Electronic spectra :

The reflectance spectra of all the uranyl complexes are almost identical with slight shifting of band positions. The complexes exhibit bands in the region 325–330 nm, 355–360 nm and 425–430 nm. The bands in the regions 325–330 nm and 355–360 nm are assigned to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. The band in the region 425–430 nm is attributed to ${}^1E_g^4 \rightarrow {}^3\pi_4$ transition typical of O–U–O symmetric stretching frequency for the first excited state. The frequencies in the region 445–460 nm may be due to the vibration of UO_2^{2+} group.

Biological studies :

The testicular atrophy caused in male albino rats by the effect of ligands L_1 – L_3 and their UO_2^{II} and Th^{IV} complexes have been studied. The results indicate that a considerable reduction in the testes weight and weights of other accessory sex organs was observed with complexes than with the ligands. Thus it is evident that these complexes have caused testicular atrophy in male albino rats.

Table 2. IR spectral bands (cm^{-1}) and their assignments in ligand and metal complexes

Compd	$\nu(\text{NH}_2)$	$\nu(\text{OH})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	Pyridine ring vibrations
L_2	–	2750b	1630s	1565m, 1460w
C_2	–	n.o. ^a	1605s	1563m, 1460m
C_5	–	n.o. ^a	1600s	1564s, 1461m
L_3	3430s, 3390m	–	1610s	1564m, 1461w
C_3	3301s, 3255m	–	1604s	1564m, 1460w
C_6	3300m, 3250w	–	1695s	1563s, 1460w

s = strong, m = medium, w = weak.

n.o.^a = not observed.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of reagent grade. Acetophenones used were distilled before use.

The Schiff bases L_1 – L_3 were synthesized by reacting acetophenone, *o*-hydroxy acetophenone, *o*-amino acetophenone with 2-aminopyridine in equimolar (0.01 mol) proportion in benzene and refluxing for 7 h followed by removal of water-benzene azeotrope¹¹. These were distilled before use. Scheme 1 shows synthetic route of ligands.

A warm ethanolic solution of uranyl/thorium nitrate (0.001 mol in 25 ml) was added with stirring to a warm ethanolic solution of the ligand (0.002 mol in 25 ml). The resulting solution was refluxed for 3 h. The complex separated on cooling was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in vacuum.

Uranium and thorium content of the complexes were determined gravimetrically as U_3O_8 and ThO_2 . Nitrogen was determined by Dumas method. The conductance measurements were made at 10^{-3} M concentrations in DMF using Elico CM-82 Conductivity Bridge. The IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 783 model in KBr pellets in the range of 4000–200 cm^{-1} . PMR spectra were recorded on WH 270 FT NMR spectrometer in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$. Diffused reflectance spectral measurements are made on Cary-d-2390 spectrometer in the range of 1600–200 nm. Good male albino rats reared under normal laboratory condition were used. After anaesthetizing, 1 ml of 0.1% each of

Schiff base, metal complexes and DMF (control) were injected to three albino rats in each case through the skin on the ventral side of the post abdomen and second injection was made through the muscle layer and the testes lying in scrotal sacaris. After 20 days, they were autopsied. The accessory reproductive organs and testes of these rats were weighed and compared.

Conclusions :

It is observed that the Schiff bases derived from acetophenone (L_1) are neutral monodentate coordinating through azomethine nitrogen, those obtained from *o*-hydroxy-acetophenone (L_2) are monobasic bidentate, coordinating through azomethine nitrogen and hydroxyl oxygen, while those derived from *o*-amino acetophenone (L_3) are neutral bidentate, ligating through azomethine nitrogen and nitrogen of amino group. A comparative study of testicular atrophy in albino rats suggest that the UO_2^{II} and Th^{IV} complexes are more toxic than the ligands.

References

1. K. B. Gudasi and T. R. Goudar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 529, 887.
2. P. B. Maravalli, K. B. Gudasi and T. R. Goudar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, **39**, 1087.
3. X. D. West and A. A. Nassar, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1998, **23**, 231.
4. N. V. Thakkar and S. Z. Bootwala, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1995, **34**, 370.
5. R. Constantinescu and R. Micusemenive, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1997, **7**, 399.
6. N. F. Curtis and Y. M. Curtis, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 804.
7. L. Guofa, L. B. Chongwu and M. Kunyuan, *Polyhedron*, 1990, **9**, 17, 2019.
8. C. N. R. Rao, "Chemical Applications of Infrared Spectroscopy", Academy Press, New York, 1963.
9. K. B. Gudasi and T. R. Goudar, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2000, **30**, 10, 859.
10. V. V. Savant and C. C. Patel, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1969, **312**, 319.
11. O. P. Singh and J. P. Tandon, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 331.